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D12.2 Disaster Risk Reduction Domain-specific FAIR vocabularies

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AHA Centre	ASEAN Coordinating Centre for Humanitarian Assistance on disaster management
ADINET	ASEAN Disaster Information Net
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMRS	Disaster Monitoring & Response System
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EM-DAT	Emergency Events Database
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDACS	Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System
HIPs	Hazard Information Profiles
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IMS	Information management systems
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
PDH	Pacific Data Hub
PDC	Pacific Disaster Center
RSMC	Regional Specialised Meteorological Centre

SFDRR	Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SPC	The Pacific Community
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
VOSOCC	Virtual On-Site Operations Coordination Centre

Executive summary

Disasters are inherently complex with wide-ranging and cascading impacts. The exponential growth in data generated daily, coupled with the complex nature of disasters, means we are hitting the limits of humans' capacity to fully exploit all the data available for disaster risk reduction (DRR). This can be addressed with well-designed, pretrained Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms that can analyse large, complex datasets and fuse heterogeneous data. However, machine-readable, semantically linked data is a precursor for the use of AI in DRR.

Nations possessing ample resources and technical proficiency are better positioned to leverage DRR data effectively, thereby potentially creating disparities in the accessibility and application of DRR data. Recent advances in technology - particularly remote sensing data, which is income-agnostic and provides global coverage - provide an opportunity to reduce DRR data gaps. Global DRR institutions should collaborate proactively with countries and regional institutions to ensure the provision of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) and open DRR data. This could help bridge any historical or emergent DRR data inequalities.

This deliverable explores the use of vocabularies in the DRR domain and how controlled vocabularies coupled with ontologies can enhance the semantic value of DRR data thereby improving interoperability. Enhancing semantic interoperability would result in improved collaboration and communication within the DRR domain and facilitate collaborations with other scientific domains. The final sections of this report provide examples of the use of remote sensing data and AI for DRR. We hope that the ideas and suggested actions in this report can be used to transform raw DRR data to valuable insights and decisions that produce tangible reductions in the impact of disasters worldwide.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	7
2. DRR information management systems	8
2.1 The Pacific Data Hub	9
2.2 Real-time disaster management and alert systems	11
2.2.1 Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (GDACS)	11
2.2.2 Sentinel Asia	12
2.2.3 ReliefWeb	13
2.2.4 Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS)	13
2.2.5 ASEAN Disaster Information Net (ADINET)	14
2.2.6 Pacific Disaster Center (PDC)	14
2.3 Information management systems and vocabularies	14
3. Vocabularies	15
3.1 UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles	15
3.1.1 Comparison of terms	16
3.1.2 Metrics and numeric limits	17
3.1.3 HIPs FAIRness	18
4. DRR data model	18
5. Satellite data	22
5.1 IPP COMMONSENSING Project	23
5.2 Sources of satellite data	23
5.3 Artificial Intelligence and satellite data	24
6. Case study: semantic data models, AI, and open data	29
7. Conclusion	30
8. Bibliography	32

1. Introduction

Large amounts of data useful for disaster risk reduction (DRR) is generated every day from sensors, satellites, individuals, and private and public organisations. In the ideal world, all these data would be FAIR and would collectively provide an interconnected network of data that can reveal crucial insights into exposure, vulnerabilities, hazards, and the efficacy of existing DRR strategies. An impediment to this is the heterogeneous nature of DRR data as it comprises data from various formats, domains, and sources, making data integration and analysis challenging. A further impediment is the complex nature of disasters. Disasters are not simple events; rather, they are a combination of multiple factors, including environmental, social, economic, and technological factors that impact people and locations differently. All these elements interact in ways that are often difficult to predict or control. Disasters often comprise cascading or simultaneous events, such as storm surge flooding and wind damage during a cyclone, or landslides triggered by seismic activity or heavy rainfall. Therefore, disasters cannot be fully understood or explained by looking at just one cause or aspect. Understanding this complexity is essential for developing effective DRR strategies.

The large amount of heterogeneous data, generated daily from multiple sources, coupled with the complex nature of disasters means we are hitting the limits of humans' capacity to fully exploit all the data available for DRR. Properly trained and well-designed AI algorithms have the potential to analyse large, complex datasets and fuse heterogeneous data. A collaboration between humans and AI is essential to fully understand the causes and impacts of disasters and to develop effective disaster mitigation and management strategies. Increasing the interoperability of DRR data, particularly semantic interoperability, will enhance AI and human collaboration.

Semantic interoperability refers to the ability to exchange data while preserving the meaning and context of the data being exchanged. In other words, it ensures that data can be understood and used correctly by different systems or users, even if they are built on different platforms, use different technologies, or have different data structures. Semantic interoperability is improved by ensuring DRR data information management systems provide FAIR data, and by using standardised vocabularies, data models, and ontologies which all help provide a common understanding of DRR data and their relationships. Increasing semantic interoperability will improve collaboration and communication within the DRR domain and between DRR and other scientific domains.

Linked¹, semantically-interoperable data is especially important for understanding cascading disaster events, where one event triggers a chain of subsequent events or multiple interconnected hazards occur simultaneously or in rapid succession. The impacts of one disaster can amplify or propagate another, leading to more severe consequences and complex challenges for response and recovery efforts. Linked and interoperable data can increase our understanding of the factors

¹ Linked data is a method of organising and connecting data on the web in a standardised and machine-readable format. <https://www.w3.org/wiki/LinkedData>

contributing to simultaneous or cascading events. Analysts and decision-makers are more able to identify patterns and causal relationships between different events and identify potential secondary hazards. This can help mitigate the potential compounding effects of cascading disasters and lead to more effective and targeted disaster management strategies.

This report focuses on how vocabularies and ontologies can be used to increase the semantic interoperability of DRR data. We begin with a description of some widely-used information systems publishing DRR data, followed by an introduction to vocabularies and an in-depth look at the recently published UNDRR hazard vocabulary (Murray et al., 2021). We then introduce a DRR data model that describes the concepts, entities, and relationships of a disaster event. Finally, we discuss how semantic interoperability can enable the use of remote sensing data to fill DRR data gaps. We finish with a case study of how AI can use vocabularies and ontologies to automatically harness remote sensing data to assist with data-driven decisions during an emergency. We hope that the ideas in this report can be used to transform raw DRR data to valuable insights and help produce effective DRR strategies that protect lives, property, and the environment from the adverse effects of disasters.

2. DRR information management systems

Information management systems play a vital role in DRR by facilitating efficient planning, mitigation, and response efforts. These systems are responsible for the collection, storage, analysis, and dissemination of information pertaining to different hazards and vulnerabilities. During crises or disaster scenarios, the accuracy and reliability of information becomes crucial for managers in making informed decisions. A DRR information management system needs an effective system for establishing and maintaining databases, ensuring their integrity and security, and keeping them current. There should be protocols and common formats for information transfer, and a robust and reliable communications network to collect information and disseminate information. It is very useful for the system to provide displays of geo-referenced information (Stephenson, 1995).

DRR information management systems can also maintain an archive of past disaster events. This archive could include a description of the hazard, satellite imagery, sensor data information, maps of the damaged region, and initial estimates of damage, infrastructure disruptions, injuries, and fatalities which can be mined to provide better information on past disasters. According to the UNDRR, the open communication and dissemination of disaster data are the bases for disaster risk reduction (UNDRR, 2014). These data can provide valuable insights and can be used in disaster risk assessment, emergency preparedness, response planning, and policy development. Analysing past disaster event data helps identify high-risk areas and vulnerable populations. Historical data can be used to develop models and simulations to predict the likelihood and potential impacts of future disasters, improving preparedness and planning and allowing policymakers develop evidence-based policies and regulations to enhance community resilience. For past disaster information to be useful

it needs to be complete, accurate, valid, up to date, and accessible. An example of DRR information systems is the Pacific Data hub which is described below.

2.1 The Pacific Data Hub

The Pacific Data Hub (PDH)² serves as a valuable tool for disaster management in the Pacific region. It provides a comprehensive collection of data and information specifically focused on the Pacific region. The PDH provides information on population statistics, climate change adaptation, DRR, resilience, and public health surveillance. The PDH platform consists of four main components: the Data Catalogue, PacificMap, PDH.stat, and Microdata Library (PDH, 2023).

- The Data Catalogue acts as the core of the PDH, managing and publishing data related to the Pacific region. It provides a search engine to access datasets. Datasets are provided in various formats (e.g., CSV or Excel spreadsheet, XML file, PDF document, image file, KML, GeoJSON, etc.) and all datasets are accompanied by metadata. The PDH follows various international standards for the required metadata fields depending on the data type.

Figure 1. Pacific map (Source: PDH, 2023)

² <https://pacificdata.org/>

- PacificMap is a web-based mapping platform that offers access to spatial data from twenty-two Pacific Island Countries and Territories (Figure 1). It integrates geospatial datasets sourced from the PDH catalogue, the Pacific Community (SPC)'s technical divisions, member countries, development partners, and other publicly-available sources.
- PDH.stat is an interactive online tool presenting a wide range of statistical indicators. It provides advanced search functionalities and a user-friendly interface to extract information from extensive data tables. PDH.Stat covers over 350 indicators, including population figures, economic indicators, social statistics, and UN Sustainable Development Goals.
- The Microdata Library allows researchers to browse, search, compare, and download relevant survey and census information from the Pacific Islands region. It provides a secure environment for data producers to disseminate survey information while ensuring compliance with policies and conditions of use³.

The PDH offers an extensive collection of 764 datasets and 11,235 publications, and involves 103 organisations. PDH stands as a crucial regional public good, serving as a centralised, authoritative source for accessing data about the Pacific. It plays a vital role in fostering investment in a sustainable data infrastructure for the region, facilitating effective data management and knowledge sharing for the benefit of all stakeholders in the Pacific (PDH, 2023). The PDH hosts datasets under a range of different licences, and most of the data available on the PDH can be accessed by anyone. Figure 2 presents the type of licences available which cater for the specific intellectual property protection requirements of the various dataset owners.

Use and access	License type		
	Private	Shared	Public (Creative Commons)
When is this Agreement used?	For access to high level, sensitive data not in the public domain (e.g. commercially sensitive).	For access and use of data not in the public domain.	For data which is publicly accessible.
How is the data accessed?	Only for authorized staff in the data portal group.	Online within and between groups on the data portal	Online through the data portal.
Can the data be disclosed to third parties?	No, disclosure to anyone may be in breach of policies and regulations in the jurisdiction of the disclosing party and in the jurisdiction of any third party to whom the data is disclosed.	No, disclosure outside of the agency may be in breach of policies and regulations in the jurisdiction of the disclosing party and in the jurisdiction of any third party to whom the data is disclosed.	Yes, as the data is already public.
Can the data be modified?	No, it is only for access.	Yes, in the exercise of the functions and responsibilities of the office.	Yes, if acknowledged and not used for commercial gain.
Do I need to give credit or attribution?	Not applicable, access only.	Yes, for internal use in the exercise of the functions and responsibilities of the office.	Yes, attribution or acknowledgement needs to be given.

Figure 2. Data License Summary Table (Source: PDH, 2023)

³ <https://pacificdata.org/terms-use>

2.2 Real-time disaster management and alert systems

This section provides descriptions of global and regional organisations providing real-time and near real-time information on disasters. They provide a good example of the provision of FAIR data. The data provided are pre-processed and delivered in machine-readable standard formats as well as formats easily used by in-country DRR practitioners and emergency response teams. The majority provide web-based mapping platforms which provide spatial information on the area impacted. These disaster alert systems can provide vital early warnings for countries with limited resources and capacity to monitor and forecast disaster events. They can also take advantage of economies of scale and allow countries to pool resources and share expertise. Archived alerts can be used for historical analysis, research, training and simulation exercises, accountability, and improving emergency management strategies.

There are good reasons to maintain both global and regional alert systems. Global disaster alert systems provide standardised early warning services over a wide geographical range and are critical for tracking disasters that can impact multiple countries or continents such as tsunamis, droughts, and volcanic eruptions. A global system can enable the rapid mobilisation of humanitarian assistance to disaster-stricken areas and can enhance the coordination among different countries and international organisations, ensuring that resources and assistance can be deployed efficiently where they are most needed. Regional systems, on the other hand, provide more localised and targeted information, ensuring that communities receive timely and relevant alerts. Regional systems can be tailored to address the specific types of disasters that are most relevant to that area. For example, a regional system in the Pacific might focus on cyclones, while one in the Mediterranean might focus on earthquakes. This ensures that the alerts are relevant and actionable for the local population.

2.2.1 Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (GDACS)

GDACS is a cooperative framework between the United Nations, the European Commission and disaster managers worldwide, that provides disaster alerts and real-time access to a web-based disaster information system and coordination tools. The system aims to fill information and coordination gaps in the first phase after major disasters. The integrated GDACS website offers the following disaster information systems and online coordination tools:

- **GDACS Disaster Alerts**, which are issued and disseminated to some 25,000 subscribers immediately following sudden-onset disasters. The automatic estimates and risk analysis, the basis of the alerts, are provided by the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC).
- **The Virtual On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (VOSOCC)** is a restricted online platform for real-time information exchange and cooperation among all actors in the first phase of the disaster. Information updates from the affected country and international responders are moderated by a dedicated team. The VOSOCC has some 19,000 registered

users and is managed by the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA).

- **Maps and satellite imagery** from various providers are shared on the VOSOCC through the GDACS Satellite Mapping and Coordination System (SMCS), which provides a communication and coordination platform where organisations may monitor and inform stakeholders of their completed, current, and future mapping activities during emergencies. This service is facilitated by the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR) and the United Nations Satellite Centre (UNOSAT).

Figure 3. GDACS disaster alerts. Source: GDACS.

2.2.2 Sentinel Asia

Sentinel Asia is an initiative for applying remote sensing and Web-GIS technologies to support disaster management in the Asia-Pacific region. Sentinel Asia is a collaborative effort among space agencies, disaster management agencies, and international agencies for sharing satellite data and imagery for DRR. Through Sentinel Asia, member countries can request satellite data and imagery for specific regions affected by disasters such as earthquakes, floods, cyclones, and other hazards. Figure 4 shows satellites currently providing observations of disasters via Sentinel Asia (Sentinel Asia, 2023).

Figure 4. Data providers and satellites included in the Sentinel Asia Constellation. Source: Sentinel Asia

2.2.3 ReliefWeb

Managed by OCHA, ReliefWeb is an online resource offering up to date information on global disasters and emergencies. Designed to support humanitarian organisations, ReliefWeb enables informed decision-making in response efforts. With a dedicated editorial team, ReliefWeb tracks and gathers data from over 4,000 critical sources. These sources encompass international and local humanitarian agencies, governments, think tanks, research institutions, and media outlets. By consolidating this vast array of information, ReliefWeb serves as a comprehensive hub for staying updated on the latest developments in disaster and emergency situations worldwide (UN, 2023).

2.2.4 Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS)

CEMS provides DRR geospatial information. By leveraging satellite, in situ (ground), and model data, CEMS offers mapping services that are instrumental in effectively managing a wide range of natural and man-made disasters including floods, forest fires, earthquakes, and industrial accidents. In anticipation of potential events, the service promptly notifies users of its findings, ensuring timely and proactive response measures. Additionally, CEMS can be activated on-demand, providing users with tailored maps, time-series data, and other pertinent information essential for enhancing disaster risk management (Copernicus EMS, 2023).

2.2.5 ASEAN Disaster Information Net (ADINET)

ADINET serves as a comprehensive repository for information related to hazards and disasters that have occurred in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) region. It operates as an open platform, allowing the public to contribute information about any hazard or disaster to the ASEAN Coordinating Centre for Humanitarian Assistance on disaster management (AHA Centre). Subsequently, the AHA Centre carefully verifies and validates the submitted information to ensure its accuracy and reliability. Additionally, the AHA Centre has the capability to incorporate new information as needed and when it is deemed relevant (AHA Centre, 2023).

2.2.6 Pacific Disaster Center (PDC)

PDC's DisasterAWARE platform delivers global early warning, hazard monitoring, and risk intelligence, providing support for disaster response, preparedness, recovery, and mitigation efforts. The system provides high-resolution all-hazards impact models, advanced analytical reports, and artificial intelligence capabilities. By integrating data from diverse sources such as weather forecasts, hazard models, and socioeconomic data, DisasterAWARE facilitates disaster risk reduction and response initiatives. It provides real-time analytics on the impacts of multiple hazards on population, capital, and critical infrastructure, enabling accurate assessment of likely humanitarian needs with high precision (PDC, 2023).

The Disaster Monitoring and Response System (DMRS) is a collaborative tool developed in partnership with the Pacific Disaster Center (PDC). It receives real-time information feeds from the PDC system, providing up-to-date data on hazards in the ASEAN region. The DMRS also includes hydrometeorological data such as wind direction and speed, cloud cover, sea temperature, and more (AHA Centre, 2023).

2.3 Information management systems and vocabularies

Information management systems involve the collection, storage, and organisation of data in a structured manner. A vocabulary can provide the terms and keywords that can be used to search for data within an information management system, enabling efficient data retrieval. Vocabularies can also help establish rules and guidelines for naming conventions, data definitions, and data relationships ensuring data consistency and accuracy across the information management system.

As outlined above there are multiple DRR information management systems currently in use. A standardised DRR vocabulary could facilitate interoperability between these systems. If all systems described above used the same vocabulary, data exchange and communication would be smoother and more reliable. However, there is always a trade-off between standardisation and providing locally relevant information. One solution may be to encourage the use of standard vocabularies and provide guidance and capacity for linking different DRR vocabularies.

3. Vocabularies

Vocabularies are essential for data integration, data exchange, and data interoperability between different systems or organisations. When multiple parties use the same vocabulary, it becomes easier to interpret and share data accurately, reducing misunderstandings and errors. When integrating data from different sources or systems, a standardised vocabulary is crucial. It allows DRR practitioners to map equivalent terms from different sources to ensure data consistency and coherence. This mapping process becomes more manageable when the vocabulary is shared and understood across all systems involved.

A vocabulary plays a crucial role in achieving semantic interoperability by providing a shared and standardised set of terms, concepts, and definitions that all participating systems can understand and use consistently. Vocabularies define the semantics (meaning) of data elements and their relationships. This semantic understanding ensures that data is not only machine-readable but also machine-understandable, enabling advanced data analysis and reasoning.

According to The Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA), FAIR vocabularies are fundamental to interoperability within domains and across domains⁴. For a vocabulary to be FAIR, it should be:

- Findable: be registered (indexed, listed) in a vocabulary service
- Accessible: be available on the web, downloadable
- Interoperable: encoded in a standard representation, such as the Web Ontology Language (OWL)⁵ or Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)⁶ and domain-specific extensions
- Reusable: licensed and maintained, ideally with an open licence

In our first deliverable⁷ we provided a list of commonly used DRR controlled vocabularies along with an overview of the main challenges they face. This section expands on the topic with an in-depth look at the recently published UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Protocols (Murray et al., 2021).

3.1 UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles

The development of the UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs) was prompted by a lack of a coherent view of hazard terminology within the DRR domain. The absence of a globally standard DRR vocabulary was compromising effective reporting which in turn reduces the DRR communities' ability to understand the cascading and complex nature of disaster risk. The HIPs project aims to reduce confusion and duplication in hazard classifications and support the use of globally-standard

⁴ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/fair-vocabularies/>

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

⁶ <https://www.ala.org/alcts/resources/z687/skos>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/7887557>

terms in DRR databases and reporting systems. (Murray, et al., 2021). The HIPs were developed using a consultative process by a working group of scientists and DRR experts across the globe.

The HIPs are comprised of 302 hazards. Each HIP contains the name of the specific hazard, a reference number, a definition, selected annotations, key references, and the name of the UN agency or organisation that issues guidance relating to the hazard. The hazards are grouped into hazard types and sub-clusters, i.e., floods are a category that includes different types of floods such as sudden onset flooding (a ‘flash flood’) or riverine flooding. The grouping is not hierarchical, and the clustering is not prescriptive as to the relationships between the hazards. Hazards can also belong to more than one category.

3.1.1 Comparison of terms

We looked at the HIPs classification for major DRR hazards to see how the HIPs categories match or align with the categories found in five widely used DRR databases: The International Disaster Database (EM-DAT)⁸, Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)⁹, International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)¹⁰, and UNDRR DesInventar¹¹. We found three major hazards where classifications differed, as shown in Table 1.

The inclusion of the climatological category in the HIPs would ensure hazards such as drought and wildfire are appropriately aligned with other DRR vocabularies and databases. In accordance with EM-DAT, the climatological category refers to hazards caused by long-lived, meso- to macro-scale atmospheric processes that span from intra-seasonal to multi-decadal climate variability; whereas meteorological hazard is caused by short-lived, micro- to meso-scale extreme weather and atmospheric conditions that last from minutes to days. The climatological category encompasses a wide range of climate-related hazards that can significantly impact communities and environments over extended periods.

Table 1. Comparison of terms in five DRR databases. Source: Tonkin and Taylor.

Terms	HIPs	EM-DAT Classification	FEMA	DesInventar Sendai	IFRC
Tsunami	Meteorological and Hydrological - Marine	Geophysical	Geological-Sourced Processes	Geological	Geophysical

⁸ <https://www.emdat.be/>

⁹ <https://www.fema.gov/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ifrc.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.desinventar.net/>

Terms	HIPs	EM-DAT Classification	FEMA	DesInvetar Sendai	IFRC
Drought	Meteorological and Hydrological - Precipitation-Related	Climatological	Hydrological-Sourced Processes	Climatological	Climatological
Wildfire	Environmental - Environmental degradation	Climatological	Hydrological-Sourced Processes	Climatological	Non-technological and man-made hazards

3.1.2 Metrics and numeric limits

The HIPs have primarily focused on incorporating the Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Wind Scale¹² as a measure for assessing tropical cyclone, typhoon, and hurricane intensity. However, different geographical regions use different wind speed-based event classification scales. For instance, the Regional Specialized Meteorological Center (RSMC) Tokyo's Tropical Cyclone Intensity Scale¹³, and the Australian tropical cyclone intensity scale¹⁴ are widely used to categorise cyclones based on their intensity and potential impacts. Including additional scales in the HIPs will provide a more comprehensive understanding of tropical cyclone intensity and its regional variations. The variety of terms and wind scales used to describe these large storm systems is an excellent example of how local customs shape DRR terminology. Rather than forcing a common standard, techniques that can easily map wind speeds to categories used in all these scales should be developed.

For the earthquake hazard, while HIPs appropriately mention the use of the Modified Mercalli scale to measure earthquake magnitudes, they do not include the widely recognised Richter Scale. Developed by Charles F. Richter in the 1930s, the Richter Scale has shaped public understanding of earthquake magnitudes and is deeply embedded in public consciousness¹⁵. Its omission in the HIPs represents a missed opportunity to bridge the gap between scientific terminology and public knowledge.

Hazards vary widely in terms of their speed of onset, their average duration, and their geographical location. This information can be vital for disaster response planning and risk assessment. However, this information is not included in the HIPs. There can be large variations in these hazard

¹² <https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/aboutsshws.php>

¹³ https://www.data.jma.go.jp/multi/cyclone/cyclone_caplink.html?lang=en

¹⁴ <http://www.bom.gov.au/cyclone/tropical-cyclone-knowledge-centre/understanding/tc-info/>

¹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richter_magnitude_scale

characteristics depending on local factors so it may be difficult to come to a global scientific consensus. This information could be extracted from global risk maps such as the UN Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction web-based risk data maps¹⁶ and the UN DesInventar Database¹⁷. The HIPs could provide references to this information. If the HIPs were provided in machine-readable format, it would be possible to automatically link to this external information.

3.1.3 HIPs FAIRness

While the HIPs is an excellent resource compiled by a dedicated team of DRR experts which has been widely peer reviewed, the HIPs is not currently a FAIR vocabulary. The FAIRness of HIPs was evaluated using the “Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR” (Cox, 2021). The vocabulary fails on many counts including:

- There are no governance arrangements or maintenance schedule.
- There are no persistent identifiers for each term in the vocabulary.
- The vocabulary is only available in PDF format and not in a standard machine-readable format.
- No metadata is supplied with the vocabulary.
- While the vocabulary does use some categories and sub-categories, there are no semantic standards applied.

The Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) is currently working to turn the HIPs into a FAIR vocabulary by implementing the “Ten simple steps”¹⁸.

4. DRR data model

A data model is a conceptual representation of data and the relationships between different data elements within a system which can easily incorporate data from multiple sources. Disasters involve numerous interconnected factors, such as geographical locations, affected populations, infrastructure damage, relief efforts, and environmental impacts. Data models can represent these relationships explicitly, enabling DRR specialists and emergency responders to understand how different elements are interrelated and how changes in one aspect might affect others. In this way, data models and vocabularies complement each other. The data model provides a visual representation of entities and relationships, while the vocabulary provides the definitions and explanations for the terminology used in the model.

Data models can also represent the flow of information during an emergency response. Critical events such as alerts, evacuations, resource allocations, and medical interventions, can be modelled

¹⁶ <https://risk.preventionweb.net/index.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.desinventar.net/>

¹⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/fair-vocabularies/>

as nodes in a data model. Visualising the flow of data can facilitate situational awareness and collaboration among response teams, ultimately leading to a more efficient and effective emergency response.

Based on a comprehensive literature review we were unable to identify an existing data model that includes concepts from all phases (prevention/mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery) of DRR. There are several examples of data models and ontologies defined for one DRR phase, particularly the response and rescue phase. A full data model for all DRR phases needs to be able to describe elements from a natural hazard or weather phenomenon, historical disaster records, expected damage model outputs, building and infrastructure material structures, statistical data on populations, and the range of human activities during each phase.

We suggest using a semantic data model such as a knowledge graph which includes elements and links between those elements. All elements included in the model should be based on entities already included in established ontologies or controlled vocabularies where possible. This would produce a data model with reasoning capabilities. Using a data model that allows reasoning will add to interoperability and allow a machine-learning approach to building a DRR knowledge base.

The DRR data model should be centred around the concept of an event that has both spatial and temporal properties. An event-based data model is well suited for DRR as disaster events are an overarching theme that connects all stages. In addition, DesInventar and EM-DAT are event-based databases. Using an event-based data model allows easier linking to these databases. A disaster event can be conceptualised as a spatial temporal event which inherits all classes and properties of a spatial object and a temporal object, i.e., it is a union of these two classes.

A natural hazard is caused by a combination of weather or geological variables over a limited time occurring at a specific location. For instance, a cyclone is defined as a storm event where wind speeds exceed a certain value and air pressure is lower than a threshold value within a bounded area. The event starts when those thresholds are exceeded and ends when they return to below the stated threshold. Then we return to normal weather, or perhaps an ex-tropical storm, which is again defined by specific thresholds. A particular measurement, i.e., wind speed at a weather station, is a measurement of a subset of those variables, also at a specific time and location. All disaster events generate multiple variables and impacts each with a specific time and location. Therefore, time and place are fundamental characteristics of any hazard or disaster data.

In our proposed data model, events can be related to other events which provides a way of defining concurrent, consequent, or compounding events. For instance, we could model a cyclone which leads to both a storm surge event and a wind damage event occurring simultaneously. The model should be capable of including a collection of events so that the model can be linked to the UNDRR Disaster Database and the EM_DAT emergency event database. Each disaster event included in the model should have an associated hazard property or properties so that each event can be linked to the HIPs and UNDRR Disaster Types and Disaster Effects.

If we have a well-defined data model, then we can query the model and answer the following questions as outlined in Worboys (2004):

- What are all the events related to object X?
- What are the objects that are related to event Y?
- Can event Y happen without object X?
- What are all the events that are related to event Y?
- What events serve as initiator events for event Y?
- How many objects serve as event-initiating or facilitating objects?
- What is the spatio-temporal setting for event Y?

Figure 5 shows an example of our proposed model based on a cyclone impacting the Pacific Island nation of Fiji. The example includes key concepts from each of the four DRR phases. Rather than inventing a new ontology, all concepts used in our proposed model are included in existing ontologies or vocabularies listed below. These are all ontologies or vocabularies that have broad semantic interoperability and are designed for commonality across domains.

- Suggested Upper Merged Ontology: YAGO-SUMO¹⁹
- Semantic Web for Earth and Environments Terminology: SWEET²⁰
- Data Catalog Vocabulary: DCAT²¹

¹⁹ <https://www.ontologyportal.org/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/ESIPFed/sweet>

²¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

Figure 5. Proposed cyclone data model. Source: Tonkin and Taylor.

NASA’s SWEET ontology is the de facto standard for the Earth and Environmental Sciences. The YAGO-SUMO ontology is the largest formal public ontology and is widely used in semantic reasoning. It is the world’s largest corpus of formalised world knowledge available for automated processing and reasoning, providing information about millions of entities such as people, cities, organisations, and companies. DCAT is a Resource Description Framework (RDF)²² vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogues published on the Web and is widely used by many national statistics departments. Table 2 shows each element in the proposed data model and their equivalent in the ontologies/vocabularies outlined above.

Table 2. Elements mapped to ontology classes

Element	SWEET	YAGO-SUMO	DCAT
Event			
Cyclone Risk Map	Map	Map	
Cyclone	Tropical Cyclone	Cyclonic Storm	
Emergency Budget	Resource Allocation	CurrencyMeasure	or

²²<https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

	Human Decision	Planning	
National Disaster Plan	Policy	Plan	
GDAC Cyclone Warning		Notification	
SMS Warning		Notification	
Rescue Worker	Human	Human or Employee or Social Role (Volunteer)	
Evacuation Centre	Building	Building	
Affected Person(s)	Human	Human. Can also be GroupOfPeople	
Damage		SubjectiveAssessmentAttribute ie non noun but an attribute of a noun	
Population Statistics		Quantity	Dataset
NMDO	Government	Government Organisation	
Early Warning System		Notification	
Evacuation	Evacuation	Evacuation	
Red Cross	Organisation	Organisation	
Time	Time		
Location	spaceLocation		

5. Satellite data

With the rapid progress in satellite remote sensing technologies and techniques, there is an opportunity to use satellite data to fill gaps in DRR data and to monitor and evaluate evolving disaster events. There is a 40-year history of regular, openly available satellite images that could be used to extract information about past events providing further information on disaster risk and the impact of past disasters.

Accurate mapping of a wide range of disaster events is now possible using satellite images. These maps can be overlaid with the locations of assets, such as buildings and farms, to provide real-time

estimates of disaster impact and populations affected. Following a disaster, satellite images can be used to help identify evacuation routes for communities, evaluate the state of roads and key infrastructure, and provide initial estimates of building damage. Images from radar satellites are particularly useful during flooding and other meteorological events as radar data is not affected by cloud cover and can be adjusted for rain and other atmospheric conditions, unlike visible light satellites which cannot penetrate cloud cover.

As well as disaster mapping, satellite images can provide an improved understanding of the built environment, including urbanisation and settlement trends, population changes, and changing infrastructure and transport needs. These data can provide information on the spatial location of buildings and infrastructure in urban and peri-urban areas. Combining this information with hazard risk maps provides an indication of potential exposure to specific disaster events.

5.1 IPP COMMONSENSING Project

The IPP COMMONSENSING Project²³ is an innovative international project based on a partnership between Fiji, Solomon Islands and Vanuatu, and a consortium of international partners, working together to support and build climate resilience and enhance decision making using satellite remote sensing technology. The project provides analysis-ready satellite data for DRR applications via the Open Data Cube²⁴, an open-source geospatial data management and analysis software project. Achievements of the project include monitoring changes to mangroves in Fiji using Sentinel-2 images, and hazard and vulnerability mapping of Honiara in the Solomon Islands. Satellites used include Landsat, Sentinel-2, ALOS-PALSAR, and the digital elevation model from the shuttle radar topography mission.

5.2 Sources of satellite data

There are currently around 1,000 satellites specifically designed for earth observation operated by government space agencies and private organisations and there have been some excellent global initiatives aimed at improving public access to these data. Many of the derived products from government satellites are freely available, and several private organisations provide free data in partnership with the European Space Agency's Earth Observation platform²⁵. Most private organisations can provide very high-resolution data at a cost. The following sources provide access to the majority of free satellite data:

- Earth Online: The European Space Agency portal. This platform hosts a collection of open satellite resources and third-party missions. The platform provides access to USA, China, and

²³ <https://www.commonensing.org.uk/>

²⁴ <https://www.opendatacube.org/>

²⁵ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway>

Japanese satellite missions and 50 satellite missions by private organisations including ICEYE, PlanetLabs's SkySat (30cm resolution), and Maxar's WorldView-3.

- Copernicus Open Access Hub: All five Sentinel missions.
- Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS): Satellite data from more than 150 national and regional providers, international organisations such as WMO, and commercial sector providers such as Digital Globe.
- Earth Explorer USGS: Provide geo-spatial data sets such satellite images from Landsat, Sentinel, IKONOS, and OrbView3, radar data, digital elevation models, aerial photos, and many other datasets. Data is served up via an interactive map where users can search by location or by inputting coordinates.
- NASA Earth Science Data: All USA government satellites as well as some third-party satellites. Access to NASA and JAXA's Global Precipitation Measurement Satellites which provides near real-time (every 3 hours) precipitation volumes anywhere on the globe.
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Wide range of US and other satellites, daily weather forecasts, severe storm warnings, and climate monitoring.
- Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) provides near real-time meteorological satellite data. The JMA provides cyclone early warning services which include modelled storm surge.
- Google Earth and OpenStreetMap provide free very high-resolution imagery.

Satellite data is currently being used to assess or monitor disaster events and their impact. Table 3 overleaf provides examples of a range of disasters and the satellites being used to monitor and assess their impacts.

5.3 Artificial Intelligence and satellite data

While satellites provide an excellent source for disaster and climate change monitoring, historically the use of such products required a high level of expertise and processing capacity making the resource out of reach of many. AI has the capability to process and analyse the large volumes of complex satellite data in a highly efficient manner. The combination of high-resolution satellite data and AI's advanced processing capabilities provides immense potential for DRR activities. There are now open-source algorithms that can be used for DRR risk assessments and monitoring disaster impacts. The code for implementing these algorithms is open and published by UNDRR Spider, ESA, and private citizens via GitHub. Listed below are some examples of AI techniques available for DRR.

- **Disaster response and management:** In cases of natural disasters, AI can use satellite images to quickly assess the extent of damage, identify affected areas and predict the likely path of the disaster.

- **Land deformation monitoring:** Deep learning models can be used to analyse radar data to monitor and predict land deformations. These algorithms can detect minute changes in the Earth's surface over time which can be indicative of phenomena such as earthquakes, landslides, or volcanic activity.
- **Drought monitoring:** There are several indicators of soil moisture and vegetation indices that can be calculated from satellite images. Using AI to process time series of satellite images is useful for identifying emerging droughts and to predict global food supplies. AI models can be trained to identify patterns associated with different soil types and crop health.

Table 3. Examples of disaster impacts currently being assessed and monitored by satellites

Element	Disaster Impact	Indicators	Satellite data source	Satellite Resolution
Health	Vector-borne disease outbreaks	Climate conditions, land cover, land use change, and water features	MODIS	Spatial: 250m, 500m, and 1,000m. Temporal: 1-2 Days
			Chinese Fengyun weather satellites	Spatial: 250 metre Temporal: GeoStationary Near Real Time
Health	Reduced quality of drinking water source	Water turbidity, chlorophyll-a concentration, water temperature	MODIS	Spatial: 250m, 500m, and 1,000m. Temporal: 1-2 Days
			Sentinel-2	Spatial: 10m Temporal: 10 Days
Supply chains	Disruption of critical infrastructure	Condition of road infrastructure, assessment of critical links in road networks, condition of port infrastructure	Synthetic Aperture Radar. Various available private and Open Sentinel-1 SAR	Spatial: millimetres Temporal: Annual – Can be on demand

Element	Disaster Impact	Indicators	Satellite data source	Satellite Resolution
Agriculture	Crop loss	Climate conditions, vegetation indices, soil moisture, evaporation rate	MODIS	Spatial: 250m, 500m, and 1,000m. Temporal: 1-2 Days
			Sentinel-1 SAR	Spatial: 10m for low level products Temporal: 6 - 12 days
			ALOS-2	Spatial: 10m Temporal: 14 Days
Bridges	Bridge damage and collapse	Deformation of bridge structure, ground instability	Synthetic Aperture Radar. Various available private and Open Sentinel-1 SAR	Spatial: millimetres Temporal: Annual – Can be on demand
Housing	Building damage, including roof loss	House height, house type, roof condition/type	Digital Globe – Often available for free following disasters	Spatial: 0.31m Temporal: Near Real Time
Forest cover	Forest loss due to fire events	Canopy height, forest moisture	MODIS	Spatial: 250m, 500m, and 1,000m. Temporal: 1-2 Days

Element	Disaster Impact	Indicators	Satellite data source	Satellite Resolution
			Sentinel-1 SAR	Spatial: 10m for low level products Temporal: 6 -12 days
Coastal erosion	Loss of coastal habitat	Erosion/accretion changes	Landsat and private satellites of higher resolution available after a disaster.	Spatial: 30m, 100m Temporal: 16 days

6. Case study: semantic data models, AI, and open data

In this section we provide a case study of the European Union’s beAWARE project²⁶ that utilises all the concepts and ideas discussed in previous sections. The beAWARE project makes use of FAIR data, semantic data models, open data, and AI algorithms to develop a decision support system during a disaster.

The main goal of the beAWARE project is to provide support in all the phases of disaster. The beAWARE knowledge base is the semantic foundation that provides the classification scheme and deduction rules and analyses information and distributes outcomes. Information is obtained from local citizens, first responders, social media, local weather forecasts, satellite data, and sensors such as in situ static cameras to monitor water levels and even cameras on drones. Citizens and first responders communicate with the beAWARE platform via the beAWARE mobile application. The social media monitoring module searches for and validates related social media content and then analyses it to perform spatiotemporal grouping of relevant posts. The smart algorithms analyse both visual and audio information. The visual analysis module can define the type of crisis, detect relevant objects (for example, cars in a flooded area) and estimate the traffic. An automated speech recognition module transcribes audio messages received through the beAWARE mobile app or phone calls in four languages (English, Greek, Italian and Spanish).

Figure 6. beAWARE system. Source: EU Docs

The Public Safety Answering Point (PSAP) is beAWARE’s central command and control system. It receives information from citizens, first responders and social media, processes it through automatic reasoning engines and analytics services and generates automatic incident reports or enriches field reports with information based on multimedia, social media, and sensor analytics.

²⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/700475>

Two field pilots; a heatwave simulation in Greece, and a flood simulation in the Italian Eastern Alps region, validated the beAWARE platform.

Figure 7. Examples from beAWARE flood simulation pilot. Source: beAWARE.

7. Conclusion

The WMO has called for everybody on earth to be covered by multi-hazard early warning systems by 2025. Early warning systems are a major component of disaster risk reduction. They prevent loss of life, as well as reducing the overall impact of natural hazards. To achieve this ambitious target the DRR community will need to fully understand the complex nature of disasters including their likely speed of onset, duration, geographical distribution, and cascading impacts. This will require the need for properly trained AI algorithms that can integrate data from multiple sources, including governments, non-government organisations, satellites, impacted citizens, social media, and sensors and other sources. This will require a DRR data revolution that transforms DRR data into FAIR and open linked data well defined by standard vocabularies and ontologies.

A collaboration between humans and AI is essential to fully exploit the large amount of data available to the DRR community as AI has the potential to analyse large complex datasets and fuse heterogeneous data. Human expertise can fine tune algorithms, identify data anomalies and errors, and create training data that accurately represent complex datasets. Experts can validate and refine AI models to ensure that generated data is accurate and usable. Future improvements in DRR will likely depend on a symbiotic relationship between AI algorithms and human expertise, where each complements the other's strengths and compensates for their weaknesses.

DRR disaster information systems and controlled vocabularies are key tools for increasing semantic interoperability of DRR data. This report proposed a disaster event centred data model for use in DRR which could be built on to include all concepts used in DRR. The advantage of a such a semantic model is that it can be linked to open data depositories, established ontologies, knowledge graphs such as DPEDIA²⁷ and Wikipedia, and standardised vocabularies. The case study demonstrated how a semantic model can use AI to access open data and to automatically conduct risk assessments and generate risk maps. This could help bridge the data gap for countries that have limited expertise or capacity in DRR.

There is already inequality of DRR knowledge between rich and poor. The insurance industry arguably holds the richest DRR data, but this is only collected from individuals that can afford insurance or who live in states that have the capacity to provide affordable disaster insurance cover. Recent advances in technology, particularly remote sensing data, which is income-agnostic and provides global coverage, provide an opportunity to reduce data gaps for lower income countries. However, unless this data is provided in a FAIR and open fashion there is the potential for the gaps to widen as countries with more resources and technical capacity make better use of DRR data. Large global DRR institutions should work closely with countries and regional organisations to provide FAIR and open DRR data and help close any historical or emerging DRR data inequalities.

²⁷ <https://www.dbpedia.org/>

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